

Deliverable 6.3

DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN

Primary Author(s)	Jennifer McIntosh (FSJD), Dace Ševčenko (BKUS), Antonio Rodríguez-Hita, Elena Dapía, Rafael Sáenz de Tejada, Jordi Ortiz, Josep Lluís Falcó (GENESIS Biomed)
Work Package / Task:	WP6 / Task 6.1.
Due Date:	31/03/2024
Delivery Date:	22/03/2024
Document Status:	Draft
Confidentiality:	PU
Deliverable Type:	R

* Dissemination Level: PU= public; SEN= sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; CO= confidential, only for members of the Consortium.

**Deliverable Type: R= report, document; Other= website, software, prototype etc.

AUTHORS

LEAD CONTRIBUTOR	FSJD
OTHER CONTRIBUTORS	BKUS, GENESIS Biomed

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR	DESCRIPTION
0.1	06/02/2024	GENESIS Biomed	First draft, exploitation Version 1.0
0.2	20/02/2024	FSJD	First draft, dissemination
0.2	14/03/2024	BKUS	First draft, communication
0.4	18/03/2024	GENESIS Biomed	Comments update exploitation Version 4.0
0.5	21/03/2024	FSJD	Final comments incorporated
1.0	21/03/2024	FSJD	Final draft ready for EC submission

INTERNAL REVIEW HISTORY

REVIEWED BY	DATE	DESCRIPTION
Katariina Gehrman	27/02/2024	Version 0.1
Pekka Kahri	27/02/2024	Version 0.1
Kathleen McGreevy	20/03/2024	Version 0.4
Beatrice Casarella	20/03/2024	Version 0.4

Disclaimer/ Acknowledgment

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	5
1. List of Abbreviations and Definitions.....	6
2. Introduction.....	6
2.1 Overview of PHEMS	6
2.2 Objectives of the plan.....	7
2.3 The PHEMS approach	8
2.4 Communication and dissemination	9
2.5 Intended audience.....	9
3. Communication Strategy	10
3.1 Target audiences	10
3.2 Key messages.....	12
3.3 Communication channels and tools	13
3.4 Branding and visual identity guidelines	15
4. Dissemination strategy	21
4.1 Dissemination objectives.....	21
4.2 Dissemination activities and channels.....	22
4.3 Creating synergies with other projects and legislation	27
5. Monitoring.....	29
6. Risk Management for Communication and Dissemination Activities	30
6.1 Risk identification	30
6.2 The risk assessment	30
7. Exploitation Strategy.....	31
7.1 European framework.....	32
7.2 Exploitation plan.....	32
7.3 Internal analysis	35
7.4 External analysis	36
7.5 Data Network Segments Across the Health Ecosystem.....	41
7.6 Potential Value Proposition and Services	42
7.7 Operational aspects relevant to the commercialization plan	43
7.8 Summary.....	43

8. Conclusions.....	44
9. References.....	46

List of Figures

Figure 1 Flow of communication.....	9
Figure 2 Business Elements in PHEMS.....	33
Figure 3 Data network across the PHEMS ecosystem.....	42
Figure 4 Main aspects to be considered for services promotion.....	44

List of Tables

Table 1 Abbreviations and Definitions.....	6
Table 2 Stakeholder Groups.....	11
Table 3 Spokespeople for targeted stakeholder outreach.....	24
Table 4 Potential European events to present PHEMS.....	26
Table 5 Communication and Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).....	29
Table 6 Key DEC Assessment.....	31
Table 7 Representative examples of European projects identified in the benchmarking.....	38
Table 8 Business models considered in the European Data Governance Act.....	40
Table 9 Potential external data customers.....	41

Executive Summary

This report provides the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) plan for the PHEMS project. It is designed to maximize the project's visibility, ensure that its outcomes are utilized effectively, and to support the project's contributions to broader societal and scientific advances. It is also designed to help guarantee the long-term success of the PHEMS project through a specific focus on stakeholder engagement and the development of a robust exploitation plan.

The communication goals, as outlined in Chapter 3, are to increase visibility and awareness amongst the targeted audience and foster engagement and collaboration with stakeholders. The communication strategy provides the framework to achieve these goals by mapping key stakeholders, developing messages tailored to these stakeholders, providing a description of the branding and visual guidelines, and outlining communication channels. The communication channels selected reflect the objective of actively engaging with specific stakeholders who will be critical to the initial success of PHEMS, while also reaching a broader audience that will support the long-term sustainability of the project.

Chapter 4 describes the dissemination strategy. The objectives of dissemination are to increase the uptake and participation of new hospitals in the PHEMS ecosystem, to demonstrate the value of the project to researchers and other innovators, and to apply the learnings of PHEMS to the development of legislation, regulations, and policies restated to health data. A key feature of the dissemination strategy is the development of stakeholder networks, based on those mapped in Chapter 2. Another key feature of the dissemination strategy is the use of hackathons to engage stakeholders, demonstrate the value of the ecosystem, and identify new applications of the PHEMS ecosystem.

Monitoring, outlined in chapter 5, will be done on a continuous basis, evaluating both communication and dissemination key performance indicators. Similarly, risk management, described in chapter 6, will also occur throughout the project to ensure successful execution of the DEC plan.

Chapter 7 presents the initial concepts for the PHEMS sustainability roadmap. The PHEMS Consortium believes that the best strategy for exploiting the results of the project is to promote services derived from the use of secondary health data through a new or already existing non-profit entity or body. This will benefit innovation, economy and businesses, and society. The chapter describes the processes that will be used to define a business model that supports the creation, scalability, and long-term operation of PHEMS. Given the novelty of this type of project and the importance of modelling the exploitation plan, an internal and external analysis will be developed in order to build a solid foundation at the beginning of the project. This analysis will be carried out during 2024 and their conclusions will be incorporated into the commercial plan and PHEMS Playbook.

Taken together the PHEMS Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication sets the stage for effective stakeholder engagement, widespread dissemination of project outcomes, and the long-term sustainability of the PHEMS initiative.

1. List of Abbreviations and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
DGA	Data Governance Act
ECHO	European Children’s Hospitals Organisation
EDAH	Interconnecting Innovation Ecosystems for Common European Data Space in Health
EHDEN	European Health Data Evidence Network
EHDS	European Health Data Space
eHDSI	eHealth Digital Service Infrastructure
EC	European Commission
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
EU	European Union
EU4CHILD	EUropean foundations for CHILdhood Cancer Ecosystem
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2O	Health Outcomes Observatory
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PHEMS	Pediatric Hospitals as European drivers for multi-party computation and synthetic data generation capabilities across clinical specialties and data types
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TEHDAS	Join Action Towards European Health Data Space
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Table 1 Abbreviations and Definitions

2. Introduction

2.1 Overview of PHEMS

This project is **focused on the secondary use of data within the European health data environment**. As a result, it aims to provide a secure and interoperable data ecosystem to data users including researchers, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and innovators.

The PHEMS project will bring together both European and UK children’s hospitals from the European Children’s Hospitals Organisation (ECHO) network with a decentralized and open health data ecosystem concept consisting of technical components and a governance

framework. The objective is to facilitate access to health data while protecting patient privacy, advance federated health data analysis, and build services for the on-demand generation of shareable, synthesized, and anonymized datasets.

To achieve this, the project will focus on bridging the gaps in data access and use, especially in the integration of ethical, legal, and technical requirements, including the responsibilities of data controllers and the rights of data subjects. This will allow health data controllers to engage in collaboration without losing control of compliance with respect to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), national legislation or internal policies of their organization.

One of the goals of the project is to assess the usage of custom-generated synthetic data with real-life questions. PHEMS has been conceived as a decentralized and open health data ecosystem concept, which overcomes important barriers and solves capability gaps that currently hinder cross-border collaboration on children's health.

2.2 Objectives of the plan

The purpose of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan is to outline a strategic approach for sharing information about the project's objectives, progress, outcomes, and impacts with a broad range of stakeholders. This plan is designed to ensure that the project's findings, innovations, and knowledge are effectively communicated and made accessible to those who can benefit from them, including the scientific community, industry partners, policymakers, and the general public.

The plan will detail specific activities, timelines, responsibilities, and tools for achieving these aims, ensuring that all project participants are aligned and equipped to contribute to PHEMS communication and dissemination efforts. This strategic approach is crucial for maximizing the project's visibility, ensuring its outcomes are utilized effectively and contribute to broader societal and scientific advancements.

Main objectives of the plan include:

- Increase visibility and awareness of the project's goals, activities, and results among targeted audiences.
- Foster engagement and collaboration with stakeholders to ensure the project's outcomes are relevant and meet the needs of various communities, including academia, industry, healthcare providers, and patient groups.
- Ensure that the knowledge generated by the project is disseminated widely and efficiently, contributing to scientific advancements, innovation, and best practices in healthcare.
- Lay the groundwork for the exploitation of project results by identifying potential applications and promoting them to relevant end-users and markets.
- Implement strategies to measure and enhance the impact of communication and dissemination activities on the project's objectives and the wider community.

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan is part of the overall activities of Work Package (WP) 6, which aims to:

- Communicate and convey a clear message about the project to all stakeholders.
- Build key stakeholder communities and organize a wide range of face-to-face and virtual events to educate about and actively engage them in the project.
- Foster communication between the PHEMS consortium and other related projects to stimulate knowledge exchange and prevent project silos.
- Produce effective, high-quality dissemination materials, creating a strong visual identity and brand reputation for excellence.
- Develop a robust business plan that will ensure the longevity and growth of the project after the grant funding has ended.

2.3 The PHEMS approach

The PHEMS Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) plan is designed to support the long-term success of the PHEMS project, with an emphasis on stakeholder engagement and participation. This approach is being taken as PHEMS is a pilot to demonstrate a proof of concept, with a limited number of hospitals and data in its ecosystem. To truly achieve its revolutionary ambition will require that stakeholders are not only aware of PHEMS but are actively taking part in it, either through joining the network or by utilizing the data within the network.

The strategy is grounded in the fundamentals of a traditional communication plan with high-quality communication materials and targeted messages, a strong visual identity, and the use of proper communication channels to reach specific stakeholders. It also includes a structured dissemination plan that will be developed to share intermediate and final results through appropriate channels. Additionally, this plan outlines strategies to actively engage stakeholders to build communities that will support the growth of the project and lay the foundations for its long-term success. Specifically, this will require:

- Support from hospitals. Data holders will need to see the value of the ecosystem and be willing to make the upfront investment to join the PHEMS network,
- A legal and regulatory environment that allows and supports the implementation of a federated data ecosystem,
- That the ecosystem provides value to external users including researchers, SMEs, or health system administrators,
- A robust business model that contributes to its long-term financial stability, and
- Trust and buy-in from patients and the general public whose data will form the basis of the project.

This plan addresses each of these needs by identifying target audiences, defining key messages, reviewing synergies to exploit with other similar projects, and mapping timelines for each. It closes with outlining plans to develop a comprehensive exploitation strategy to sustain and grow the project once the initial grant funding has ended.

2.4 Communication and dissemination

Communication activities include developing guidelines, a corporate design, a collaboration platform, and materials such as videos and press releases to share information about the project.

Dissemination and knowledge transfer activities involve sharing results through various channels, including the media, publications and social networks, and creating a knowledge transfer library.

These efforts aim to raise awareness, promote synergies, and support the project's long-term sustainability and impact. The specific definitions of communication and dissemination as used in the project context are implied through these described activities, focusing on spreading information and engaging with stakeholders to ensure the project's success and uptake.

The flow of communication within the PHEMS project is designed to ensure a seamless exchange of information among project partners, stakeholders, and the broader public. This involves a structured yet flexible approach to how information is created, shared, and received (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Flow of communication

2.5 Intended audience

This document is intended mainly for the PHEMS consortium partners and related organizations or individuals contributing to key DEC activities.

3. Communication Strategy

3.1 Target audiences

Achieving the aims of PHEMS will require continuous communication, trust-building, and collaboration between stakeholders. One of the key activities within the PHEMS DEC strategy is to develop stakeholder communities who will support the development, scaleup, and long-term sustainability of the project.

Table 2 maps key stakeholder categories with specific sub-groups listed where applicable. Communication and dissemination materials and activities will be specifically targeted at these groups.

Stakeholder Groups	Description
<i>Individuals whose data will be part of the ecosystem</i>	
Children, families, and the general public	Individuals or the families of those receiving care at children's hospitals or health members of the public whose data might one day be used in the PHEMS ecosystem but are not currently patients
Patient associations	Associations representing populations or people with specific disease states that will benefit from the PHEMS ecosystem such as young people or those with rare diseases
<i>Hospitals who hold data</i>	
Children's and research hospital managers	Individuals within a hospital in charge of setting hospital strategy and determining budget priorities such as the CEO or director
ICT professionals	Professionals within a hospital responsible for the development and maintenance of hospital information and communication technology (ICT) strategy, implementation, and maintenance
Clinicians & pediatric clinical services	Health care professionals or heads of services who will use the new tools to treat patients and who will continue using and growing the data ecosystem in the future
Data controllers	Professionals involved in maintaining the security of patient data in accordance with national and European law
<i>External parties who will want to use the PHEMS ecosystem</i>	
Researchers	Academics and scientists from multiple disciplines including healthcare, public health, or data science who will use the data ecosystem to conduct new research and create new learning
Small and Medium Enterprises	Businesses that will potentially use the data ecosystem to develop new products or help test existing products
<i>Those shaping the legal and regulatory data landscape</i>	
Health authorities	European and national authorities charged with developing and implementing policies related data protection, health data sharing, and artificial intelligence (AI) such as the European Commission (EC)
Other data ecosystem initiatives	Regional or national initiatives to develop data standardization and sharing across hospitals and healthcare systems

Table 2 Stakeholder Groups

3.2 Key messages

The following section outlines key messages formulated for effective communication and engagement with various stakeholders:

1. Enhancing research through federated analytics

Objective: Increase knowledge of federated analytics and its possibilities.

Key message: The PHEMS project introduces a new model that enables faster and easier access to data for researchers, revolutionizing the way healthcare research is conducted by leveraging federated analytics. This model facilitates seamless collaboration and data sharing across research hospitals, significantly reducing the time and complexity traditionally associated with accessing diverse datasets.

Target audience: Research hospitals.

2. Benefits of joining the ECHO network

Objective: Communicate the benefits of joining the ECHO network.

Key message: Joining the ECHO network offers unprecedented access to new federated methods to access data, empowering children's hospitals to leverage a broader spectrum of healthcare data. This collaboration enhances the ability to implement innovative healthcare solutions and improves patient care outcomes.

Target audience: Children's hospitals.

3. Unveiling PHEMS project achievements

Objective: Communicate the benefits of the PHEMS project.

Key message: The PHEMS project's findings from clinical use cases provide valuable insights into improving healthcare services and patient outcomes. These advancements showcase the project's commitment to enhancing pediatric healthcare through data analytics and federated learning approaches.

Target audience: Pediatric services.

4. Personal stories of impact

Objective: Communicate personal stories of children.

Key message: "We were able to provide better care" – sharing personal stories from children and their parents to highlight the tangible benefits and improvements in care resulting from the PHEMS project.

Target audience: Children and their parents.

5. Engaging youth in science and data analytics

Objective: Discuss with youth about science, data, AI, and similar topics.

Key message: Showcasing the PHEMS project's work and engaging with youth to gather their feedback, fostering a connection with the next generation of scientists and innovators.

Target audience: User advisory groups – Youth Scientific Committee.

6. Addressing environmental impacts

Objective: Communicate the environmental impacts of advanced data analytics.

Key message: Highlighting the environmental implications of data analytics, including the carbon footprint of AI training, to raise awareness and drive actions towards reducing the healthcare sector's environmental impact.

Target audience: Researchers and hospital management.

7. Fostering innovation collaboration

Objective: Increase innovation collaboration.

Key message: The PHEMS project shares new data resources with researchers and local innovators, encouraging collaboration and the development of new medical technologies and solutions.

Target audience: Local innovators and MedTech companies.

3.3 Communication channels and tools

Digital Presence and Online Platforms

- **Project website www.phems.eu:** A central hub for disseminating project information, updates, and resources to the public, stakeholders, and consortium members, the website is developed and designed to be easily updated with the latest information and new sections as necessary (such as the Knowledge transfer library). This flexibility ensures it can grow and evolve in tandem with the project.

Initially the website features the following sections:

The Project: Provides an overview of the PHEMS project, its significance in the European healthcare sector, and its innovative approach to pediatric health data management. This section includes following:

Objectives: Details the specific goals the project aims to achieve, focusing on improving healthcare outcomes and creating a more integrated and efficient healthcare system in Europe.

Data Ecosystem: Describes the PHEMS project's efforts to revolutionize health data management across Europe through patented technology for anonymizing data, creating new synthetic datasets, and applying machine learning to federated data.

Work Packages: Outlines the different work packages within the project, including project management, platform architecture, data processing, clinical use case validation, governance, dissemination and exploitation, and ethics requirements.

Partners: Lists the partners involved in the PHEMS project, showcasing the collaborative effort across various institutions and organizations.

News: Features updates and news related to the project, keeping stakeholders and the public informed of progress and developments.

Contact Us: Provides contact information for inquiries and further information about the PHEMS project

- Social media: The project’s LinkedIn page to disseminate project results, engage with the community, and promote events: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phems>

- The EU Health Policy Platform is an interactive tool to stimulate discussion about public health concerns and provide an easy way for stakeholders to share knowledge and good practices. This platform will be used to publicize events such as online webinars and distribute communication materials to a broad range of stakeholders.
- Internal collaboration platform: An internal – MS Teams - area for secure consortium communication and an external platform for public engagement.

Multimedia Tools

- Video content: Development of video to showcase project results and explanatory content on professional and social media platforms.
- Informational material: Creation and maintenance of publishable material such as brochures, posters, and infographics to communicate project milestones and results.

Public relations and outreach

- Press releases: Communication of intermediate results, important milestones, and achievements through media.
- Participation in events: Attendance and presentation at trade fairs, conferences, seminars, workshops, and exhibitions relevant to the project's objectives.

3.4 Branding and visual identity guidelines

The branding strategy for the PHEMS project includes creating a logo and icon that reflect the project's values, aiming to establish a clear visual identity. Presentation templates, a graphical guide for the portal, and other dissemination tools were developed following a branding guide. This approach ensures consistent communication and dissemination of the project's results, both during its active phase and after its completion, maintaining coherence in how the project is presented and perceived externally.

Branding guide

Guidelines for the PHEMS project have been established, covering the use of the project's logo, icons, and the creation of both traditional and digital documents in the future.

Project Logo

Brand icon

Brand fonts

PRIMARY

Montserrat

Laconic and practical typeface

Collective of authors: Julieta Ulanovsky,
Sol Matas, Juan Pablo del Peral,
Jacques Le Bailly
2017

Primarily intended to use the typeface
Light, Regular, Medium and Bold
versions.

Availability:
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat/about>

Aa
Aa

SECONDARY

Arial

A modern san serif typeface. Practical and widely applied.

Authors: Robin Nicholas, Patricia Saunders
1982

Use the typeface as a secondary one in business
correspondence, for digital documents. Primarily
intended to be used Regular and Bold versions of the
typeface.

Availability:
<https://www.fonts.com/font/monotype/arial>

Aa
Aa

Brand colors

RGB 51 142 172
CMYK 70 22 16 0
HEX #338eac

RGB 221 138 52
CMYK 0 44 80 0
HEX #dd8a34

RGB 42 185 171
CMYK 67 0 38 0
HEX #2ab9ab

Dissemination tools

Text Document (Letterhead, Press releases, Formal invitations etc.)

PRESS RELEASE
16.10.2023.

EU awards large funding to develop data-driven collaboration between European Pediatric Hospitals

PHEMS project will advance data-driven research and innovation activities in pediatrics and the use of privacy-preserving datasets in Europe. The project's aim is to overcome important barriers that currently hinder cross-border collaboration on health data by developing and validating a decentralized health data ecosystem. This will enable an ecosystem without central data repositories or release of sensitive personal health data from hospitals.

A consortium led by HUS Helsinki University Hospital has received significant EU funding for developing data collaboration between European Children's Hospitals in a privacy-preserving manner. Progress in this area will help the development of new therapies for children, the assessment of pediatric care outcomes and the advancement of new technology solutions such as artificial intelligence in pediatrics. The project will start in October 2023 and go on until September 2026. It has been awarded a total funding of 7 ME from the Horizon Europe programme and from the UK research funding agency.

"We will enable European collaboration on health data by aligning ethical and legal requirements of leading European pediatric hospitals with the needs of data users. This ensures that researchers can benefit from rich datasets and advance scientific research in pediatrics while the patient's rights and data privacy remain protected" states Katriina Gehrmann, Director of Digital and Innovation Services at HUS New Children's Hospital.

To achieve this, the project develops new technological solutions that facilitate authorized access to health data at multiple locations and advances federated health data analysis together with next-generation anonymization. In addition, the project develops shared rules and governance structures, which allow new partners to join and new datasets to be included in the ecosystem.

"One challenge with algorithmically anonymized and synthesized datasets is the lack of evidence on their validity and utility for real-world needs in research or healthcare management. Therefore, we shall perform studies on three clinical use cases and aim to generate evidence in different clinical areas and in the management of healthcare operations" continues Gehrmann.

The Consortium consists of six leading European pediatric hospitals from the European Children's Hospital Organization (ECHO) community and of leading-edge technical partners. The ECHO community advocates for children's health and their access to the best quality care through the collaborative work of children's hospitals.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The consortium hospital partners are HUS Helsinki University Hospital (Finland), Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam (Netherlands), Meyer Children's Hospital IRCCS in Florence (Italy), SJD Barcelona Children's Hospital (Spain), Great Ormond Street Hospital for Children in London (United Kingdom), Bērnu klīniskā universitātes slimnīca (Latvia) In addition to Children's Hospitals, the PHEMS consortium includes technology partners: Tietoevry Finland Oy (Finland), Aridhia Informatics Limited (UK) and VEIL AI Oy (Finland) and two professional services partners: The Hyve B.V. (Netherlands) and GENESIS Biomed (Spain). The proposal preparation was supported by company specialized in EU-funding, namely Spinverse.

For more information:
Katriina Gehrmann,
Director of Digital and Innovation Services,
Children and Adolescents, HUS
katriina.gehrmann@hus.fi, tel. +358 40 730 7741

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Report, research template

Deliverable XXXX

TITLE: XXXX

Primary Author(s)	
Work Package / Task:	WPX / Task X.X
Due Date:	
Delivery Date:	
Document Status:	Draft / Final
Confidentiality:	CO / SEN / PU
Deliverable Type:	R / O

* Dissemination Level: PU= public; SEN= sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; CO= confidential, only for members of the Consortium.

**Deliverable Type: R= report, document; Other= website, software, prototype etc.

AUTHORS

LEAD CONTRIBUTOR	
OTHER CONTRIBUTORS	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR	DESCRIPTION

INTERNAL REVIEW HISTORY

REVIEWED BY	DATE	DESCRIPTION

Disclaimer/ Acknowledgment

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

PHEMS PowerPoint template

The image displays a variety of PowerPoint slide templates for the PHEMS project. The templates include:

- Agenda:** A blue slide with the PHEMS logo, the word "Presentation", and "Presenter".
- Title:** A white slide with a blue header, a title box, and a text area.
- Text:** A white slide with a blue header, a title box, and a large text area.
- Timeline:** A blue slide with a white header, a title box, and a vertical timeline with colored diamond markers and text boxes.
- Team:** A white slide with a blue header, a title box, and three columns for team members, each with a "Click icon to add picture" instruction and fields for Name, Title, and Text.
- Partners:** A blue slide with a white header, a title box, and a grid of partner logos including ECHO, GENESIS Biomed, SJD, HUS, and others.
- Thank you!:** A blue slide with a white header, a title box, and fields for Name Surname and Organisation.

PHEMS project presentation slides

phems

Pediatric **H**ospitals as **E**uropean drivers for **M**ulti-party computation and **S**ynthetic data generation capabilities across clinical specialties and data types

Funded by the European Union

An urgent need for timely and safe data sharing

- **Small numbers of complex pediatric and rare diseases patients per country**
 - Limited ability to conduct research, develop new therapies, and improve patient outcomes
- **Limited real-world data for newer expensive therapies**
 - Health technology assessment (HTA) bodies lack data and processes to evaluate treatment outcomes
- **Need for more engagement with MedTech Industry & Innovation ecosystems**
 - Large data sets are needed to leverage benefits of artificial intelligence and machine learning and support innovation
- **Many countries only have one or two children's hospitals**
 - Shared data are necessary for benchmarking to improve system performance and efficiency

phems

Funded by the European Union

- 3-years** October 2023 - September 2026
- 7 M€** Funded through Horizon Europe and UK Research & Innovation
- 14 partners** including hospitals, universities, technology, and biotech companies

Coordinated by **HUS**

Funded by the European Union

Partners

- Hospitals and Universities**
 - Erasmus University Rotterdam
 - S3D San Joan de Déu
 - HUS
 - ECIO
 - GENESIS
 - GENESIS
- Technical and Business**
 - The Hyve
 - Tietoevery
 - GENESIS

phems

Funded by the European Union

PHEMS transcends boundaries, supporting access and use of health data between children's hospitals and across borders

- Objectives**
- Increase access to health data while protecting patient privacy
 - Advance federated health data analysis through predictive modeling and machine learning
 - Enable on-demand generation of shareable synthetic and anonymized datasets
 - Demonstrate the value of the data ecosystem using three clinical use cases in four countries

The project will create a decentralized and open health data ecosystem consisting of technical components and governance frameworks, empowering institutions to collaborate without relinquishing control over their data.

phems

Funded by the European Union

Project Overview

Demonstrating impact: clinical cases

- Cardiology operations benchmarking**
Supporting creation of benchmarking standard and promote a culture of benchmarking across pediatric cardiac institutions, enabling the adoption of 'best-practice' across institutions
Led by Great Ormond Street Hospital for Children (GOSH)
- Pediatric Intensive Care Unit Sepsis**
Investigating the benefits of the federated ecosystem to develop, train and test algorithms to predict sepsis on a large scale units in four large European children's hospitals
Led by Sant Joan de Déu Barcelona Children's Hospital (HSD)
- Hematology - hemophilia**
Developing and testing a machine learning-based prediction algorithm to improve treatment for pediatric patients with hemophilia A or B
Led by Erasmus University Medical Center Rotterdam (Erasmus)

The clinical cases use OMOP harmonized pediatric data from different hospitals, contributing to new clinical and organizational knowledge

Funded by the European Union

If data is GDPR compliant it can be utilized in many use cases

Project Organisation

Thank you!

Name Surname
Organisation
www.phems.eu

Funded by the European Union

Other visual elements: Zoom background and social media post example

4. Dissemination strategy

4.1 Dissemination objectives

The focus of the dissemination and exploitation activities is to promote and facilitate the use of project results. Activities target stakeholders that may use the results in their own work, such as hospitals, researchers, innovators, or policymakers. The goals of the PHEMS dissemination activities are to:

- Increase uptake and participation of new hospitals in the PHEMS data ecosystem;
- Demonstrate the value of the project to researchers and other innovators such as MedTech, Pharma, and SMEs;
- Apply the learnings of PHEMS to the development of legislation, regulations, and policies regarding health data.

4.2 Dissemination activities and channels

Building stakeholder networks

Achieving the dissemination objectives of PHEMS will require building stakeholder networks. Reaching key stakeholders and building connections will necessitate the application of individualized strategies. This will involve targeted messaging (described in Section 3.2), reaching stakeholders in the right settings and via spokespeople that convey trust and legitimacy.

Hospital Outreach

Hospitals are the primary outreach target, as increased participation of data owners is critical to the long-term success of the project. Outreach to hospitals will follow a semi-tiered approach as the project matures. Although outreach is planned in stages, this will not be a strictly linear process and there will be overlap between “stages”.

- **Initial stage – ECHO member hospitals:** Create a core group of “non-PHEMS” ECHO member hospitals with a clear understanding of the project and the requirements to join in the future.
- **Second stage – European outreach:** Reach out via a snowball approach with invitation to ECHO member peer hospitals within Europe and connect with national children’s hospitals organizations (e.g. Children’s Hospital Alliance, UK; the Italian Association of Children’s Hospitals (*Associazione Ospedali Pediatrici Italiani (AOPI)*)).
- **Third stage – international outreach:** Continue the snowball approach with invitations to ECHO member peer international hospitals while connecting with children’s hospitals organizations in Canada (Children’s Healthcare Canada), Australia (Children’s Healthcare Australasia), and the United States (Children’s Hospital Association) to invite participation in the ecosystem.

Policy Maker and Health Authority Outreach

Policy makers and health authorities are also one of the primary targets for dissemination. Outreach and relationship building will begin early in the project and will initially build on existing relationships within the PHEMS consortium and will grow organically based on contacts within PHEMS. Initial targets include Commission staff currently involved in developing the regulatory framework for the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and Sitra, the coordinator of the upcoming joint action on the EHDS.

Patients and the General Public

Although patients will not be directly applying the results of PHEMS to their work in the classical interpretation of dissemination, it is important that they are part of the dissemination plan. Patient advocacy groups and the general public must see the value in the project as it relates to their health and feel comfortable consenting to the use of their data. Patients may also have unique and innovative ideas for applications of the ecosystem. Outreach to patients and patient advocacy organizations will also follow a tiered approach,

with the initial outreach focused on larger patient-advocacy organizations already active in the health data space, and later activities focused on patients and the general public.

- **Initial stage:** Outreach to European-level patient organizations including but not limited to EURODIS, Childhood Cancer International Europe, European Patients Forum, and representatives from the European Reference Networks.
- **Second stage:** Outreach to Young Persons Advisory Groups and patient and family advisory groups within ECHO member hospitals.

Researchers and External Data Users

This group of stakeholders includes internal researchers within hospitals, external researchers in academia or research institutes, as well as those from industry such as MedTech, Pharma, or smaller SMEs. Outreach to these stakeholders will occur later in the project once the data ecosystem is more mature and there are preliminary results from the use cases. Outreach to these stakeholders will be done via contacts within the PHEMS network as well as via professional conferences and meetings.

Spokespeople

When building stakeholder networks, peers will be used for communication whenever possible to ensure the highest quality information is being conveyed and that the messenger has legitimacy in the eyes of the audience. This includes presentations as well as one-on-one meetings. When peers are not used, peer groups will be consulted to ensure that the materials and messaging resonates with the audience. Table 3 provides examples of potential spokespeople and peer reviewers.

Knowledge transfer

Knowledge transfer will take place in a variety of formats depending on the audience.

Scientific papers

During the project, the partners will produce **at least three scientific, peer-reviewed publications addressing various aspects of the project**. Publications create a public record of the work, lend legitimacy, increase visibility, and help lay the foundation for future collaborations.

Specific topics for publications will depend on the results and learning developed during the course of the project but in general they will address:

- Results of the clinical use cases;
- Advancements in the application of AI and machine learning to healthcare management and patient care;
- The impact of PHEMS on healthcare systems and care management.

The target audience for scientific papers are primarily researchers, innovators, and to a certain extent policymakers. Journals for publication will be selected based on the reputation of the journal with the intended audience. All publications will comply with the EC open-access policy and acknowledge European funding of the project.

Stakeholder Groups	Examples of Spokespeople or Peer Reviewers for Outreach Materials
<i>Individuals whose data will be used</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients and the general public Patient associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hospital youth and family advisory councils within PHEMS hospitals Young Persons Advisory Groups at PHEMS hospitals
<i>Hospitals who hold data</i>	
Children's hospital managers	Director-level positions such as the PHEMS Project Coordinator or ECHO Executive Director
ICT professionals Data controllers	PHEMS technical partners
Clinicians	PHEMS clinical use case partners
<i>External parties who will want to use the PHEMS ecosystem</i>	
Researchers	Researchers in the PHEMS network, authors of publications
MedTech, Pharma, SMEs	PHEMS Project Coordinator or technical partners (depending on the scope)
<i>Those shaping the legal and regulatory data landscape</i>	
Health authorities	Director-level positions such as the PHEMS Project Coordinator or ECHO Executive Director
Other data ecosystem initiatives	To be determined based on the specific needs of the presentation

Table 3 Spokespeople for targeted stakeholder outreach

Knowledge transfer library

In addition to the publication of scientific papers, an online library containing white papers, policy briefs, and executive summaries will be developed as part of the PHEMS website. The goal of this library is to be agile and develop interim products that can be produced as the project matures. Given the slower pace of scientific publishing, this library will be important for the dissemination of interim project results. Products within the online library will include:

- **White papers and policy briefs:** Recommendations to policy makers on requirements for current and future legislation and regulations on health data spaces will be made to ensure maximum benefit to patients while creating a favorable environment for researchers and SMEs. Specific topics and numbers of briefs will depend on how various legislation and regulations progress, but it is anticipated that **at least one white paper will be published with supporting policy briefs developed as needed.**
- **Executive summaries:** As project deliverables are produced, executive summaries using language appropriate for the target audience will be developed summarizing relevant points. Example topics for executive summaries include but are not limited to descriptions of the system architecture, the governance framework, or the playbook.

- **Use case abstracts:** The clinical use cases are one of the most important aspects of PHEMS for demonstrating the value of the project in a real-world setting. Therefore, it will be important to communicate interim results before full scientific publications are available. As researchers publish abstracts of interim results at scientific meetings (see below), these will also be made available in the knowledge transfer library.

Events

Attending scientific conferences and other meetings is an important way to communicate the results of the project, both through formal channels such as abstracts or oral presentations as well as informally through networking with colleagues.

Table 4 lists potential events that PHEMS will attend. All events are held annually, and the schedule of attendance will be determined by the availability of project results.

Event	Description
IoT Week	IoT Week is a one-of-a-kind 4-day conference where leaders from the worlds of business, tech and science shed light on the future of technology and its impact on business and life.
Pediatric Innovation Day	A one-day conference bringing together innovators, investors, and practitioners to promote maternal and pediatric innovation including new applications of digital technologies.
Mobile World Congress	Mobile World Congress Barcelona is the largest and most influential event for the connectivity ecosystem
AEPC	Annual Meeting of the Association for European Paediatric and Congenital Cardiology
ESPNIC	Annual conference of the European Society of Pediatric and Neonatal Intensive Care
ESCIM LIVES	Annual conference of the European Society of Critical Intensive Medicine
Tecnosepsis	International meeting of innovation in sepsis care
HIMSS	European Health IT event, where professionals throughout the health ecosystem connect for education, innovation, and collaboration.
IoT solution world Congress	An event highlighting digital transformation trends and disruptive technologies with input from thought leaders with a focus on business impact.
Digital around the World	For 24 hours non-stop, region by region, time zone by time zone, top-level international speakers will be presenting and discussing the last technological innovations and trends in digital transformation.
eHealth Investment Forum	An annual event focusing on the investment, development, and uptake of digital health solutions.
XPatient Barcelona Congress	A community of practice that brings together institutions from the hospital, technological, research and administrative fields to discuss how technology can transform the healthcare model and place the patient in the center.
Future Health Summit	This internationally distinguished event is an Irish and international gathering of the brightest minds in the healthcare industry with an audience of over 600 high-end industry delegates attending, including representatives from Ireland, USA, UK, Europe, and beyond.
Medica Trade Fair	The world of medicine meets at MEDICA. A must for anyone who wants to experience tomorrow's healthcare market live.

Table 4 Potential European events to present PHEMS

Trainings

To demonstrate the ecosystem's utility, train stakeholders in its use, and prepare hospitals to join the ecosystem, the project will hold a series of live and online training sessions. These will be tailored to the needs of previously described stakeholders, with the specific topics being developed in conversation with representatives from each stakeholder group. Example topics include:

- Introduction to PHEMS
- Standardizing your data using OMOP (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership)
- Technical requirements: Getting your hospital ready
- Patient's role in AI research and data protection

Experts from the PHEMS consortium will develop and present the sessions. Meet-up will be held online bi-monthly and then recorded and uploaded into a YouTube channel for broader distribution.

Hackathons

Hackathons will be organized around several themes generated by learning that takes place within the project. Goals of the hackathons include engaging external stakeholders, demonstrating the value of the ecosystem, identify new applications for the ecosystem, and testing the security of the ecosystem. PHEMS will hold **at least two hackathons, one scheduled for the project's end when the results from the use cases are available and the other(s) scheduled during the project's second half.**

4.3 Creating synergies with other projects and legislation

Multiple other projects have similar or overlapping objectives to PHEMS. It is important that we are in communication to create alignment, share learning, help catalyze the actions of each other, and reduce redundancies. Another potential benefit of cross-communication between projects will be the development of joint input on upcoming legislation and regulations in the health data space to ensure new legislation and regulation creates a supportive environment for projects like PHEMS.

The PHEMS consortium has identified an initial list of projects and policy initiatives related to the project. This list will be updated and revised as the project matures. Below is a summary of projects related to PHEMS grouped by category that we will be following and working with throughout the life of the project.

Projects funded by the same Horizon Europe call

By nature, these “sister” projects will have similar objectives to PHEMS and it will be important to share learning and promote each other's activities.

- PHASE IV AI (Privacy Compliant Health Data As A Service For AI Development): <https://www.phase4ai-project.eu/>
- FLUTE (Federate Learning and mUlti-party computation Techniques for prostate) cancer: <https://www.fluteproject.eu/>
- AISym4MED (Synthetic and scalable data platform for medical empowered AI): <https://aisym4med.eu/>
- SECURED (Scaling Up secure Processing, Anonymization and generation of Health Data for EU cross border collaborative research and Innovation): <https://secured-project.eu>

- SYNTHEMA (Synthetic generation of hematological data over federated computing frameworks): <https://synthema.eu>

A communication network amongst these projects has already been established. The goal of these meetings is to ensure ongoing momentum and discuss further collaborative strategies. These meetings will also serve as a platform to share results and brainstorm new ideas that could benefit all projects involved.

General data

Projects that are addressing similar technical issues including data harmonization, AI, and federated data.

- UNICA4EU: <https://unica4.eu/>
- TEF-HEALTH: <https://tefhealth.eu/home>
- European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN): <https://www.ehden.eu/>
- Gaia X: <https://gaia-x.eu/>
- QUANTUM (data quality & utility label, yet to be launched)
- Privasa: <https://privasa.eu/>
- Data space support center: <https://dssc.eu/>

Clinical initiatives

Projects sharing clinical data.

- The Health Outcomes Observatory project (H2O): <https://health-outcomes-observatory.eu/es/>
- OKER (PICU Oncology Kids in Europe Research group) from ESPNIC (European Society Pediatric and neonatal intensive Care): <https://www.hetwkz.nl/en/research/researchers/wosten-van-asperen-roelie-rm/research-output>

Policy related projects and legislation

Initiatives that will influence, directly or indirectly, the legal and regulatory environment that PHEMS operates in.

- European Health Data Space: https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en
- DARWIN-EU: <https://www.darwin-eu.org/>
- TEHDAS joint action: www.tehdas.eu

Other

i4KIDS-Europe: <https://www.innovation4kids.org/en/>

5. Monitoring

Monitoring of communication and dissemination activities will occur continuously throughout the project. After the DEC plan launch, quarterly monitoring will take place on the key performance indicators (KPIs) listed in Table 5. This will allow us to determine whether we are reaching our target audiences and make course adjustments in our strategies if we are not. In addition to summarizing the KPIs, a full report on the results of the hackathons will be produced at the end of the project summarizing the knowledge gained from these events.

Indicator	KPIs
Number of unique contacts with hospitals outside the PHEMS consortium via meetings, presentations, workshops or other activities	Reach 100 hospitals
Number of unique contacts with children's hospitals in Europe outside the PHEMS consortium via meetings, presentations, workshops or other activities; number of these hospitals signing on to the PHEMS governance agreement	Engage with 12 hospitals, with at least 2 hospitals initiating implementation beyond the PHEMS partners
Number of unique contacts with representatives from pediatric cardiology, intensive care, or hematology-hemophilia services (count per service, not per individual)	Reach 30 services
Number of individual children, young people, and parents reached	Reach 100 children, young people, and parents
Number of meetings with youth advisory groups or youth scientific committees	Hold 5 meetings
Number of unique meetings with researchers working on the impact of the environment and health	Engagement with the research community and commitments for CO2 emissions reduction
Number of unique meetings or interactions with MedTech companies	Meet with 50 MedTech companies at various events
Number of papers published in peer reviewed scientific journals	A minimum of 3 articles will be published
Number of white papers published targeting policy makers	A minimum of 1 white paper will be published
Number of hackathons conducted	A minimum of 2 hackathons will be conducted
Number of LinkedIn posts published over the course of the project to share updates, insights, and outcomes with the professional community	Publish at least 50 LinkedIn posts
Number of press releases issued to disseminate project milestones and significant achievements	Issue at least 3 press releases
LinkedIn followers yearly increase	30% increase in followers

Table 5 Communication and Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

6. Risk Management for Communication and Dissemination Activities

The implementation of the DEC Plan for the PHEMS project involves various activities subject to potential risks. Effective risk management is crucial to identify and monitor these risks, ensuring the successful execution of the plan.

6.1 Risk identification

- **Message misinterpretation:** The risk that communication messages are misunderstood or misinterpreted by different stakeholders.
- **Stakeholder engagement shortfalls:** The risk of failing to engage the targeted stakeholders sufficiently, impacting the project's visibility and uptake.
- **Technological failures:** The risk associated with the use of digital platforms and tools for communication and dissemination, including website downtime, Microsoft Teams malfunction or social media outreach limitations.
- **Regulatory and compliance risks:** The risk of non-compliance with data protection and privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR) in communication materials and activities.
- **Intellectual property (IP) issues:** Risks related to the inappropriate sharing of sensitive or proprietary information.

6.2 The risk assessment

The risk assessment is designed to evaluate the likelihood (the probability of the risk occurring within the project's timeline) and impact (the potential severity of the risk's effect on the project's DEC objectives and overall success) of identified risks associated with the DEC activities of the PHEMS project. Table 6 describes risks for the DEC plan.

Risk	Likelihood	Impact
Message misinterpretation	Medium. Given the complex nature of health data projects, there's a significant chance of misinterpretation, especially when communicating with a diverse audience.	High. Misinterpretation can lead to loss of stakeholder trust, reduced engagement, and potential backlash, affecting the project's reputation and adoption.
Stakeholder engagement shortfalls	Medium. Extensive planning has gone into stakeholder engagement, but variability in stakeholder responsiveness and interest levels poses some risk.	High. Inadequate engagement can limit the project's visibility, decrease the effectiveness of dissemination activities, and hinder the identification of potential exploiters or collaborators.
Technological failures	Low. Digital platforms are selected for communication and dissemination, though risks remain due to external factors like service outages.	Medium. Temporary disruptions may delay information dissemination but can be mitigated with prompt action and backup communication channels (for example, e-mails).
Regulatory and compliance risks	Low. The project is committed to adhering to all relevant regulations, including GDPR.	High. Non compliance can result in legal penalties, loss of stakeholder trust, and significant damage to the PHEMS project's credibility.
Intellectual property issues	Low. The risk exists in inadvertently sharing sensitive or proprietary information without adequate safeguards.	High. This can lead to legal disputes and loss of competitive advantage.

Table 6 Key DEC Assessment

7. Exploitation Strategy

This chapter presents an initial approach to define a business model (also known as business strategy). The following outlines the context in which the business model will be developed and the framework that will be used including an internal and external analysis. As the project progresses, we will advance the development of the business model with the addition of both qualitative and quantitative data via interviews and surveys. All of this will help contribute to the long-term sustainability of the PHEMS ecosystem and ensure it continues after the initial grant-funded period ends.

7.1 European framework

In order to define a feasible business model which enables a successful exploitation of the data, various external factors such as the European Health Data Space should be considered.

According to the European Commission, **the [European Health Data Space](#) is a health specific ecosystem comprised of rules, common standards and practices, infrastructures and a governance framework for both primary and secondary data use.**

Primary use of health data consists of using health information of an individual to drive its own healthcare pathway, such as diagnosis or selection of treatments. An example of European initiatives to improve digital access and control of personal health data for primary use includes “MyHealth @ EU”, which is based on the eHealth Digital Service Infrastructure (eHDSI), an infrastructure to exchange health data in a secure, efficient, and interoperable way.

However, the focus of PHEMS goes beyond the primary use: PHEMS will be based in the secondary use of health data and records, providing a consistent infrastructure for the **use of health data for research and innovation, policy-making and regulatory activities.**

An illustrative example regarding secondary data use is the TEHDAS project, a joint action of 25 member states to support the implementation of the EHDS by developing and promoting concepts for the secondary use of health data to benefit public health and health research and innovation in Europe. Other EHDS related projects in the context of secondary use of data include the HealthData@EU which aims to build a pilot version of the EHDS infrastructure, and QUANTUM, a coordination and support action to define the data quality, utility and maturity label to be used in the EHDS.

7.2 Exploitation plan

Business concepts

Receiving a grant from the Horizon Europe program enables the development of new technologies and to bring these technologies closer to society. If there is no adequate business plan for its exploitation, all the efforts made within the project can be wasted. There are three key concepts to consider when considering the long-term sustainability of a project: exploitation plan, business plan and commercialization plan. Figure 2 is an illustration of the relationships among them.

Figure 2 Business Elements in PHEMS

The Exploitation Plan defines ideas and trends (the strategy to reach the market) that will be developed in the Commercial Plan and are in line with the Business Plan. Both documents are still under development and require the participation of the various project work packages, reflecting the high degree of interdependency and collaboration in PHEMS.

The exploitation plan involves **all of those aspects that will impact not only on the level of technology transfer of the assets**, but also on the **economic sustainability of the ecosystem itself**, starting by asking the following question: **what are the key assets of the project?**

Once there is some consensus on the project's assets, **it is appropriate to carry out an external and internal analysis to design the exploitation plan.**

All of the above are closely linked to the governance model as the set of principles and rules governing the design, integration and operation of PHEMS ecosystem.

Exploitable assets

At this early stage of the project, there is still uncertainty about the future exploitable assets. Nevertheless, through the various meetings and interactions with the project partners, some consensus has been reached on the main assets of the project. Below is a

summary of the potential assets that will be consolidated and defined during the life of the PHEMS project.

Software copyright

The source code of the software could be protectable under copyright law. In order to determine the autonomous entity of the work, it will be important to determine whether or not it has been derived from the use of other open-source software. It is also important to bear in mind that copyright law may vary in different countries of the European Union (EU). The difference between continental and Anglo-Saxon copyright law is significant because the continental system places significant importance on the individual as the author of the work.

In EU countries, copyright protects IP until **70 years** after death of the author. Copyright grants economic rights (the possibility of obtaining remuneration) and moral rights (the right of attribution as author and the right to refuse modification of the work by a third party).

This copyright could be transferred by the right holder(s) by license agreement to the entity responsible for exploitation.

Know-how

In a project as complex as PHEMS, prior knowledge is invaluable. Know-how encompasses a broad range of expertise and knowledge required to successfully operate and utilize the network for different purposes. By combining technical, operational, and clinical skills, PHEMS stakeholders will create a secure, efficient, and valuable ecosystem for advancing research, improving healthcare delivery, and ultimately benefiting patients. Know-how will be another asset at the end of the project.

A trade secret is any information or knowledge, including technological, scientific, industrial, commercial, organizational or knowledge which meets the following conditions:

- a) it is secret.
- b) It has business value, either actual or potential, precisely because it is secret; and
- c) It has been the subject of reasonable steps taken by the holder to keep it secret.

Given the public function, it is understood that one of the values of the ecosystem will be transparency and that most of the relevant aspects (governance model, legal agreement models, pricing of services, etc.) will be public. However, there might be some elements that could be kept as trade secrets, competitive advantage, or know-how.

Services

As we will analyze in later sections of this report, services related to data access, visualization and exploitation constitute a value proposition for ecosystem users. Consequently, these services are susceptible to exploitation.

The internal costs of each offered service will be quantified and the fee will be calculated according to potential operating margins. Tariffs could be reduced for certain user profiles including original consortium partners, small companies, researchers.

The recurrence of the fee could also vary and support different models such as pay-per-use, monthly payment, or annual payment.

Furthermore, in addition to secondary data access, the PHEMS project will materialize a set of infrastructure protocols, data access and anonymization algorithms and know-how, among others, that would be incorporated into the ecosystem's service offerings.

Data

The possibility to access an interoperable pool of data for exploitation for secondary use is the driver of the PHEMS project. In a knowledge economy, stakeholders (researchers, clinicians, innovators, and companies) need reliable data to improve health-related products and services.

Network

This project brings together a rich network of data providers, technology providers, and users. This network aims to grow as the project consolidates. This network is instrumental in creating a pool of reliable and interoperable data.

Ecosystem

All the assets described above (software copyright, services, data, and network) could be grouped together under this concept.

7.3 Internal analysis

To identify relevant business models, a key step is understanding the data value chain, its layers and its principal functions.^{1,2} Setting up PHEMS involves interaction between various stakeholders and the integration of interests of many parties. PHEMS' stakeholders will provide unique insights as per their role in the PHEMS ecosystem, e.g., by highlighting areas where the PHEMS solution will add value. This section will analyze aspects such as:

- Introduction to the hospitals, ECHO, and SMEs that are part of PHEMS.
- The relevance of knowing partner's individual/collective interest in exploiting the solution.
- Analysis of previous IP and partner's contribution to new IP proposals, created within PHEMS project.
- Identify institutional differences or gaps in policy, as differences in institutional processes are to be expected in leadership, legal, and technical teams. This aspect will be developed in WP5 (Governance and Playbook).
- Potential legal restrictions preventing the Institution its participation in for-profit initiatives. In this respect, the main question to respond to is will the ecosystem allow the data and the models derived from its use to be used for commercial purposes?
- Services to offer (contribution) per partner and costs.
- Interest in continuing to participate in the network and role after the PHEMS project has ended.

The activities to be carried out in the operational plan to achieve sustainability will need interdependencies and inputs from the ecosystem architecture, the development of a governance framework, the playbook, as well as the rest of activities of WP6. Finally, this analysis will be carried out by means of a survey to understand whether there is capacity and interest from partners to exploit the ecosystem, exploring the interest of the partners in taking a leading role in the exploitation or becoming part of a legal entity for jointly exploiting and continuing to develop the assets after the end of the project, existent intellectual/industrial property knowledge or rights that may affect the exploitation model, etc.

7.4 External analysis

In addition to the internal analysis to identify the interest and capabilities of the partners in exploiting the assets of PHEMS, an external analysis is required to identify if there is a market demand of what PHEMS can offer, if there are other comparable projects or initiatives with similar aims that could influence the exploitation, and if the project is aligned with the current legal frameworks.

Total Available Market Demand^{3,4}

Adherence to the regulations and standards outlined in the European Data Governance Act (DGA) will be strictly followed in approaches within the primary healthcare market. The extensive compilation of health data, viewed from a patient-centered perspective, will serve as a foundation for developing prevention strategies and algorithms. These advancements aim to improve public healthcare through the application of machine learning and AI approaches.

The European Union's data market is projected to achieve a value of **€116 billion** by 2030, demonstrating a Compound Annual Growth Rate (**CAGR**) of **3.4%**. Within this outlook is the expectation to see the gradual establishment of a robust data ecosystem centered around diverse vertical and horizontal industrial, as well as personal data platforms. These platforms aim to facilitate secure environments for sharing and trading data. The successful development of European Data Spaces within the EU27 is expected to play a pivotal role in providing secure channels for data exchange and trading across major industries. Against this backdrop, the European data industry is poised for rapid expansion. **By 2030**, the number of **data supplier companies** is estimated to reach **around 313,000**, exhibiting a cumulative growth rate of 3.5%, slightly outpacing the growth rate of the overall data market. Projections indicate that by 2030, data supplier companies will constitute 2.5% of the total companies within the ICT and professional services sectors, an increase from the 2% reported in 2022. Simultaneously, the number of data user companies is anticipated to experience growth, propelled by the widespread adoption of AI and data-driven business models by large enterprises and innovative SMEs. By 2030, the EU27 is expected to have **906 thousand data user companies**, reflecting a cumulative growth rate of 6.9% for the period spanning 2025 to 2030. This surge will result in the data users' share of the total universe of EU enterprises reaching 3.2% in 2030, a notable increase from the 2.2% reported in 2022. According to the impact assessment for the EHDS proposal, the **global**

digital health market has seen a steady increase in terms of size from **€16 billion in 2015** to **€31 billion in 2020**.

Finally, the global COVID-19 pandemic has expedited the gathering of genetic and health-related information on a global scale, with China experiencing a particularly significant surge.

Benchmarking Analysis Topics

Business models

Considering the growth of the data market, a benchmarking analysis is being performed with the aim of exploring the more widespread business models for data sharing and set a starting point based on previous experiences. As a search methodology, the team has combined an *organic search* in regular search engines with a *structured search* in the CORDIS portal to detect calls funded by the European Commission. A combination of different keywords ("data", "sharing" and "federated") was used on the CORDIS portal. The focus has been set in the technology and type of the shared data; however, results were not limited only to pediatric data.

The search had the objective of identifying all the publicly available information related to the established business models in other cases of data sharing in healthcare mainly in Europe, due to closer regulations. Additionally, projects focused on creating the framework for the European health data space (e.g., EDAH or TEHDAS) have been detected as relevant for the ecosystem and considered for the establishment of an effective business model.

This initial assessment yielded a total of *29 potentially relevant projects*. However, this number is expected to be updated for the final commercial plan to have a broader scope of what has already been implemented and set the basis for what could be implemented soon. Differences in the business model are being considered and evaluated as each business model is aligned with the respective playbook, the ecosystem values, and the interest of the involved parties.

To exemplify some of the implementation pathways found during the analysis, three relevant projects have been listed in Table 7 with their available information regarding their future sustainability.

Project	Description
Towards European Health Data Space (TEHDAS) ⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Allows to charge fees for secondary use of the data (proportionate to the costs) – Possibility of tiered fees (e.g., depending on the quality of the data)
European Health Data Evidence Network (EHDEN) ⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Harmonization and standardization of real-world health data across Europe – EHDEN portal: platform to facilitate data sharing, collaboration, and healthcare data analysis among various stakeholders (researchers, healthcare providers, policymakers) – Network of certified SMEs and Academia (Data Partners), responsible for converting local data bases into OMOP Common Data Model – Innovative Medicines Initiative project ending in April 2024 – Sustainability beyond 2024 as a new not-for-profit entity based on non-competitive research collaboration with data partners, academia, and industry to address research needs; and on services and tools (e.g., data catalogue) to improve data interoperability through data standardization, standardized analytical pipelines, tools to share study results and tools for stakeholder engagement and training
European foundations for Childhood Cancer Ecosystem (EU4CHILD) ⁷	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Digitalization of pediatric cancer data to overcome data silos and the reluctance to share health-related data – Combination of advanced anonymization and encryption, federated infrastructures for distributed training of AI models, harmonization, and standardization of data sources – Exploitation: Results and tools used will be delivered to UNICA4EU – Since EU4CHILD is a preparatory action, its results are mostly linked to knowledge related results that are expected to be generated by the consortium over its implementation period
Health Outcomes Observatory (H2O) ⁸	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – European network for the collection and analysis of Patient Reported Outcomes – Operating as a non-for-profit network of entities, charging for value added services on top of the outcomes data – Income streams through products and services: analysis across countries of current outcomes and trends in outcomes linked to outcomes relevant clinical data items on a pay to access or subscription model to regularly published updates; or access to aggregated anonymized data sets – Supply-side actors would not be expected to pay for outcomes insights but would access such analytics as part of their in-kind value chain (Incentives)

Table 7 Representative examples of European projects identified in the benchmarking

Most relevant projects in the field of health data sharing are in **early stages of development** (e.g., preparatory actions), most of which do not have an established business model to ensure project sustainability. As most of the projects have not reach their ending date, and thus, their not-financed stage, **they will be monitored** during the following period.

Some of them advocate the **development of open-source tools** and the **creation of new entities for the exploitation of the results, mainly not-for profit entities**. The not-for-profit status is a key aspect for the collaboration of healthcare organization to share data, as well as providing **transparency** about the business models. Nevertheless, **being a not-for-profit organization does not prevent the charging of fees to cover costs**.

These initial findings revealed that sustainable business models for decentralized open health data ecosystems are limited, confirming the innovative nature of PHEM's project.

Legal framework

The legal framework is important because it will directly affect the scope of the results exploitation plan by determining obligations or prohibitions.

This legal framework could be divided between the legal and contractual obligations arising from the project itself (e.g., grant agreement) and those arising from EU regulations.

Grant agreement

According to Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement of PHEMS, "**Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must — up to four years after the end of the action— use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.**"

This annex also provides for the following: "*The beneficiaries may transfer ownership of their results, provided this does not affect compliance with their obligations under the Agreement.*"

The beneficiaries must ensure that their obligations under the Agreement regarding their results are passed on to the new owner and that this new owner has the obligation to pass them on in any subsequent transfer.

Moreover, they must inform the other beneficiaries with access rights of the transfer at least 45 days in advance (or less if agreed in writing), unless agreed otherwise in writing for specifically identified third parties including affiliated entities or unless impossible under the applicable law. This notification must include sufficient information on the new owner to enable the beneficiaries concerned to assess the effects on their access rights. The beneficiaries may object within 30 days of receiving notification (or less if agreed in writing), if they can show that the transfer would adversely affect their access rights. In this case, the transfer may not take place until agreement has been reached between the beneficiaries concerned."

European data governance act

Most of the provisions of the EU Data Governance Act 2022 became fully applicable across the EU on 24 September 2023.

This regulation explicitly describes four business models associated with the data (Table 8).

Data altruism	Fee collection
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entities may use the common logo designed for this purpose and may choose to be included in the public register of data altruism organizations. Regime with some advantages (visibility, EU support, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More focused on public sector bodies. The fee only covers costs, it does not allow for profit generation. Possibility to give discounts or free of charge to different types of users (SMEs, researchers, etc.).
Data intermediation services	Services of data cooperatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More focused on companies. Commercial purpose (profit generation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data intermediation services offered by an organizational structure constituted by data subjects, one-person undertakings or SMEs who are members of that structure. Commercial purpose (profit generation)

Table 8 Business models considered in the European Data Governance Act

Regulation of the European health data space

Although this regulation is still at the proposal stage it will be the cornerstone of the European health data space and will consequently affect the PHEMS exploitation plan.

There is an inclination to protect the specific interests and needs of SMEs, public bodies, Union institutions, bodies and agencies involved in research, health policy or analysis, educational institutions and healthcare providers (**fee reductions**).

ECHO statutes

ECHO is a new and growing organization representing many of the leading children's hospitals across Europe. It is one of the project partners and the one that, in principle, has the most attributes to become the exploitation entity. The statutes define ECHO's internal rules of operation. In art. 1 it describes itself as a non-profit entity. However, this provision would not be an impediment to collecting fees based on DGA. This fact will require a final validation and alignment from ECHO's Board of Trustees.

Market Analysis Strategy

Considering all the previous information, and to garner authentic feedback from potential data consumers interested in PHEMS, it is essential to showcase examples of the services they could potentially acquire. The initial step involves cases studies, utilizing either fictional data or anonymized data from partner sites, illustrating the primary services that the network aims to provide. The primary focus will be on exemplifying fee-based services, emphasizing specific contributions to health and research ecosystems rather than more general offerings from observatories.

These examples, based on pediatric care areas, like **cardiac patient pathways, pediatric intensive care unit sepsis prediction, and hematology/hemophilia**, will serve as a starting point. While interacting with potential customers, efforts will be made to explore additional services. Despite potential variations across data consumers, the initial expectation is that returns will be generated by services such as (non-exhaustive list of potential examples):

- Regularly performed analyses across countries of current outcomes, and trends in outcomes, linked to outcomes of relevant clinical data items for each of the disease areas, in the case of PHEMS: Cardiac patient pathways (healthcare operations management, predicting sepsis in patients at the pediatric intensive care unit and Hematology / hemophilia.
- Access to the federated health data ecosystem, which would be curated by the Governance Institution according to European DGA, and made available for query analysis by data customers, for example, to profile pediatric patient outcomes when designing a research study such as a trial protocol, platform trials in diseases target mentioned in the point 1 studies.
- PHEMS could facilitate recruitment of pediatric patients for a prospective observational or interventional study, with recruitment and data collection.
- Copies of anonymized data sets that have been robustly checked, mirroring the European DGA.

7.5 Data Network Segments Across the Health Ecosystem

PHEMS offerings have the potential to attract a diverse array of organizations and sectors within the health ecosystem. This market analysis aims to explore the perspectives and opportunities across various public and private entities. While a comprehensive list of customer segments for future surveys is under development, an initial categorization is included in Table 9.

INDUSTRY	PUBLIC BODIES
Pharma	Health ministries
Biotech	Health insurance
MedTech, health ICT	Regulators, HTA
Algorithm developers	Regional health authorities, healthcare provider networks
Data analytics companies	National and multinational policy-making bodies (e.g., WHO, OECD)
Data brokers	Healthcare professional associations
SMEs, particularly app developers	Patient organizations and other charities
Consulting companies in the health and life sciences sectors	Academic research organizations and non-governmental organizations

Table 9 Potential external data customers

HTA: Health Technology Assessment, ICT: Information and Communication Technology, OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; WHO: World Health Organisation

As mentioned above, an example structure is proposed in Figure 3. This structure is crucial for analyzing and visualizing complex relationships across the PHEMS ecosystem.

Figure 3 Data network across the PHEMS ecosystem

7.6 Potential Value Proposition and Services

The clinical use cases and the future interactions of the actors will define the core services. It is therefore important to stress the changeable nature of these services, as they will evolve according to the needs of data users and the capabilities of data providers.

Future regulations may also condition the scope of core services as well as the future financial needs of the ecosystem.

In addition to the core services emanating from ecosystem governance, there could be a sort of "free trade zones" in which some operators could offer other complementary services.

- Activities in WP2, WP4, WP5 and use cases will shed light on operational costs of the hospitals.
- Benchmarking: It appears there is no economic return to data providers. The benefit to data providers comes from their own research, audit, and analytical needs, and, they benefit from partnership opportunities, training and easier scientific collaboration.

- The sources committed will serve as a basis for cost planning and product pricing. The development of the project will provide insight into the size of the investment required for a commercial launch.

7.7 Operational aspects relevant to the commercialization plan

Sustainability could be achieved either by hosting and operating the network through one of the members of the consortium or through setting up a new entity that will be engaged in hosting and operating the network. PHEMS targeted customers must be analyzed, to **segment**, in an efficient way, the existing and the potential customers, and to design the market strategy to improve its effectiveness.

The type of entity in charge of the exploitation, the licensing agreements required for this entity to exploit the results and type of revenue are the main points to consider for the operation and commercialization.

Type of entity

In addition to using the legal personality of an existing partner (e.g., ECHO) a **new legal entity could also be created**. By way of illustration, a foundation or an association could be set up. It is important to take into consideration that depending on the adapted legal form (company, association, foundation, etc.) some incentives such as tax advantages may be available.

The country in which the entity is located will also be relevant, as the applicable regulations for an association or non-profit entity will vary accordingly.

Licensing agreements

In case IP rights are generated, a licensing contract will have to be drawn up by the owner(s) of the exploiting entity. This contract should establish the considerations (e.g., royalties) as well as the scope of the license (e.g., exclusivity, sub-licensing, etc.).

Type of revenue

The final commercialization plan should be designed to support the creation, scalability, and long-term operation of decentralized and open health data ecosystems. Other aspects, as the **type of institution** (academia/industry) and **scope of the research** (public/for profit) will be considered.

7.8 Summary

This chapter addresses the main aspects to be considered in the operating plan for the services offered by a decentralized (federated) health data network like the PHEMS ecosystem, taking into account long-term sustainability and scalability requirements. As detailed in Figure 4, the existence of an **exploitation entity**, that could be a not-for-profit entity as ECHO, will play a major role on the sustainability of the network by offering assets, as a data catalogue, in exchange for fees in order to cover operational costs.

This project has just started, and all activities are in a germinal state of development. The elements discussed in this report will be developed during the project and will be included in report D6.4 Commercialization plan.

Figure 4 Main aspects to be considered for services promotion

8. Conclusions

The Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan for the PHEMS project is designed to ensure the successful outreach and impact of the project’s outcomes across the European health data ecosystem and ensure its long-term sustainability. This plan not only outlines a structured approach to effectively communicate with and engage a diverse set of stakeholders but also shows the project’s commitment to transparency, collaboration, and innovation.

Throughout the implementation of this plan, the project team will adhere to principles of clarity, accuracy, and inclusiveness, ensuring that all communications are understandable, accessible, and relevant to the intended audiences. The plan's focus on leveraging a variety of channels and activities – from web site and LinkedIn to workshops, webinars, and hackathons – aims to maximize reach and engagement, fostering a vibrant community around the PHEMS project.

The risk assessment and management strategies embedded within the plan demonstrate a proactive approach to identifying and addressing potential challenges that could impact communication and dissemination efforts. By continuously monitoring and adjusting these strategies, the project ensures resilience and adaptability in its outreach activities.

This document also addresses the long-term sustainability of the project with the elaboration of an exploitation plan that accounts for the value of future services the ecosystem could offer and scalability requirements.

The execution of this Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan will not only support the immediate goals of the PHEMS project but will also contribute to building a sustainable framework for the future use and sharing of health data across Europe. This project has the potential to influence broader policy discussions, technological advancements, and collaborative models in the health data domain.

In conclusion, the PHEMS Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan is a strategic and dynamic document that will evolve alongside the project. It sets the stage for effective stakeholder engagement, widespread dissemination of project outcomes, and the long-term impact of the PHEMS initiative.

9. References

1. World Economic Forum. Sharing Sensitive Health Data in a Federated Data Consortium Model: An Eight-Step Guide [Internet]. 2022 Jul. Available from: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Sharing_Sensitive_Health_Data_2020.pdf
2. Hallock H, Marshall SE, 't Hoen PAC, Nygård JF, Hoorne B, Fox C, et al. Federated Networks for Distributed Analysis of Health Data. *Front Public Health*. 2021;9:712569.
3. Micheletti, Giorgio, Raczko, Nevena, Moise, Cristina, Osimo, David, Cattaneo, Gabriella. European Data Market Study 2021–2023. D2.5 Second Report on Policy Conclusions. [Internet]. 2024 Feb. Available from: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/results-new-european-data-market-study-2021-2023>
4. European Commission. Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space. [Internet]. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52022PC0197>
5. TEHDAS Consortium. Sustainability Plan for Secondary Use of Health Data in the European Health Data Space [Internet]. 2023 Sep. Available from: <https://tehdas.eu/app/uploads/2023/09/tehdas-sustainability-plan-for-ehds.pdf>
6. Rijnbeek, Peter, Hughes, Nigel, Prieto, Daniel, Wiener, Mathew, Lamb, Alan, Toulas, Jimmy. D5.5 Report Federated Network Studies. 2021 Oct.
7. Gangas, Pilar, Alvarez, Arturo, Lyne, Fiona. D4.3 Impact, exploitation and sustainability Final Report [Internet]. 2022 Oct. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/10477842>
8. Kolitsi, Zoi, Kalra, Dipak, Styliadou, Meni. D6.12 H2O exploitation and sustainability strategy [Internet]. 2021 Apr. Available from: https://health-outcomes-observatory.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/H2O_D6.12_H2O-exploitation-and-sustainability-strategy.pdf